

COMPOSITION OF CUPRIC *o*-CRESOTATE CHELATES: A COLORIMETRIC STUDY

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Copper^{II} forms chelates with *o*-cresotic acid. In 1:1 mixtures of cupric sulphate and monosodium *o*-cresotate, the green colour intensifies on increasing the p_H , and maximum colour is obtained at p_H 5.2. The composition of the complex has been determined at p_H 5.2 and 5.0, which indicates the formation of a green complex containing cupric ion and *o*-cresotate in 1:1 ratio.

In 1:2 and 1:3 mixtures of cupric sulphate and monosodium *o*-cresotate, the colorimeter readings show maximum at p_H 5.7, which indicates the formation of some complex other than 1:1. The composition of this complex has also been determined by Job's method at p_H 5.7, and it contains cupric ion and *o*-cresotate in 1:2 ratio. In between 5.7 and 5.2, intermediate mixtures of the two complexes exist.

Copper salicylate complexes have been investigated by Babko (*J. Gen. Chem. U.S.S.R.*, 1947, 17, 443) by Job's method (*Ann. chim.*, 1928, x, 9, 113; Vosburgh and Cooper, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1941, 63, 437). Turner and Anderson (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1949, 71, 912) studied the copper sulphosalicylate complexes spectrophotometrically.

EXPERIMENTAL

Standard solutions of cupric sulphate were prepared by direct weighing of an Analar-B D.H. sample of copper sulphate ($\text{CuSO}_4 \cdot 5\text{H}_2\text{O}$) and dissolving it in water. Fresh solutions were always prepared to avoid effects due to hydrolysis.

The monosodium salt of *o*-cresotic acid was prepared as described by Tripathi and Prakash (this issue, p. 119). Standard solutions of monosodium *o*-cresotate were prepared by direct weighing of the prepared sample.

All the measurements were made at a constant temperature of $30^\circ \pm 0.1^\circ$. p_H and colorimetric measurements were made as in the case of complex formation of uranyl ion with *o*-cresotic acid (Tripathi and Prakash, *loc. cit.*).

Complex-forming Systems.—To study the complex formation of copper^{II} with monosodium *o*-cresotate, monovariant method was used as in complex formation of uranyl ion with *o*-cresotic acid (*loc. cit.*).

To study Job's method of continuous variation, different mixtures of Cu^{2+} and monosodium *o*-cresotate were prepared in various ratios at constant p_H 's of 5.20, 5.0, 5.7 and 5.4. The p_H 's of the mixtures were raised by alkali. The total volume of each mixture was kept 50 c.c. The colorimetric measurements of the mixtures were made with filters Ks42 and Ks 47 within the transmission ranges of 400–450 $m\mu$ and 455–505 $m\mu$ respectively after the attainment of equilibrium.

DISCUSSION

In the graphs the abscissa represents the p_H or the ratio of the concentration of monosodium *o*-cresotate to the total concentration of monosodium *o*-cresotate and cupric ion, while the ordinate represents colorimeter readings.

Fig. 1 shows the changes in colour with the rise in p_H in 1:1, 1:2 and 1:3 mixtures of 0.0667*M* cupric sulphate and 0.0667*M* monosodium *o*-cresotate. Colorimeter readings with filters Ks 42 and Ks 47 have been plotted against p_H .

The two curves in Fig. 1-A show that increase in colorimeter readings takes place by the addition of alkali up to p_H 5.2 in 1:1 mixtures of Cu^{2+} and monosodium *o*-cresotate; after that precipitation of copper hydroxide starts and is complete at about p_H 8.0. Inference can be drawn from this that a green coloured complex is formed in the systems containing Cu^{2+} and *o*-cresotate, most probably in 1:1 ratio.

As the maximum in colorimeter readings is at p_H 5.2 (Fig. 1-A) the formation of the complex may be presumed at p_H 5.2, and above this p_H the complex breaks up.

For the determination of the composition of the complex, Job's method (*loc. cit.*) was used; 0.0667*M* cupric sulphate and 0.0667*M* monosodium *o*-cresotate solutions were mixed in various ratios (0.1 to 1.0) of the concentration of monosodium

o-cresotate to the total concentration of monosodium *o*-cresotate and Cu^{2+} ion. The p_{H} of each mixture was raised to a constant value of 5.2 by alkali and the total volume was kept at 50 c. c. in each case (Fig. 2). From the examination of the two curves A and B (Fig. 2) of two filters Ks 42 and Ks 47, it is clear that maximum in colorimeter readings lies at the ratio of 0.5, indicating the formation of a green complex in 1 : 1 ratio of cupric sulphate and *o*-cresotate at p_{H} 5.2.

FIG. 3

FIG. 2

Fig. 3 shows the graphical representation of colorimeter readings of the mixtures containing Cu^{2+} and monosodium *o*-cresotate in various ratios at constant p_{H} 5.0, keeping the total volume in each mixture constant at 50 c. c. Here also the colorimeter readings show maximum at the ratio of 0.5, indicating the same 1 : 1 ratio complex of cupric ion and *o*-cresotate.

When alkali was added to the mixtures containing cupric sulphate and monosodium *o*-cresotate in the ratios of 1 : 2 and 1 : 3, the green colour of the mixtures deepened (Fig. 1, B, C). The maximum intensity of the green colour in both sets of 1 : 2 and 1 : 3 mixtures was at a somewhat higher p_{H} than that of 1 : 1 mixture (Fig. 1, A). The colorimeter readings showed maximum at p_{H} 5.7, indicating the formation of a different complex but not of 1 : 1 ratio. This complex was not stable above p_{H} 5.7 and cupric hydroxide was precipitated above this p_{H} .

FIG. 5

FIG. 4

The composition of the complex at p_H 5.7 by Job's method with mixtures containing (0.0667M) cupric ion and (0.0667M) monosodium *o*-cresotata (Fig. 4) was determined. The colorimeter gave maximum readings at the ratio of about 0.7, indicating the presence of cupric ion and *o*-cresotata in 1:2 ratio in the complex. It can be presumed that the hydrogen of monosodium *o*-cresotata is displaced in the complex formation and co-ordination takes place with oxygen atoms of hydroxyl and carboxyl groups. It can be concluded that this 1:2 complex is a chelate of the following structure :

The colour maximum of the mixtures of various ratios of cupric ion and monosodium *o*-cresotata at constant p_H of 5.4 is at the ratio of 0.65 (Fig. 5). At p_H 5.4, the intermediate mixtures of both the complexes are present.

It becomes quite clear from the above observations that cupric ions form two green-coloured complexes with monosodium *o*-cresotate. One complex is formed up to p_H 5.2 containing cupric ion and *o*-cresotate in 1:1 ratio and the other complex at p_H 5.7 containing cupric ion and *o*-cresotate in 1:2 ratio. The 1:1 ratio complex breaks up above p_H 5.2 and 1:2 ratio complex, above p_H 5.7.

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